

An Improved the Fractional - Order Accumulated Grey Model by Trigonometric series and Its Application in Tourism Industry

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Abstract: - In order to improve the prediction accuracy of fractional- order accumulated Grey model ($GM^r(1,1)$), this study using one of special class of orthogonal series called Trigonometric series to modify their residual error of this model. To verify the effectiveness and the contribution of the proposed approach, the number of tourist visits to Quang Ninh from 2011 to 2022 is used for the modeling to forecast the tourism demand from 2025 to 2028. Forecasted results provided that the proposed model will be enhanced by 1.79% prediction accuracy compared with $GM^r(1,1)$ model. This result is not only show the effectiveness of proposed model but also offers valuable insights for Quang Ninh policymakers in orientation and planning management agency so as to boost the development of upcoming tourism activities.

Keywords: - *Fractional-order accumulated Grey model; Trigonometric series; forecasting, accuracy; tourism; Quang Ninh province*

1 Introduction

Grey forecasting is a key component of grey system theory and serves as an effective method for modeling and forecasting time series with small sample sizes. In the early 1980s, Deng [1] introduced the grey model $GM(1,1)$, based on control theory, which remains the core model within grey forecasting. This model applies a first-order accumulation operator to the non-negative original sequence, revealing approximate exponential growth patterns and enabling accurate short-term forecasts. Due to its ability to handle uncertain information and its effectiveness with as few as four data points [2], $GM(1,1)$ has been widely validated and applied across various fields, including tourism [3], transportation [4; 5], finance and economics [6; 7], the integrated circuit industry [8; 9], and the energy sector [10; 11].

In recent years, numerous scholars have proposed various enhancements to improve the prediction accuracy of the $GM(1,1)$ model. For example, Lin et al. [12] and Wang et al. [13] introduced alternative methods for calculating background values to enhance model reliability. Hsu [9] and Wang et al. [14] focused on refining the estimation of internal parameters, such as the development coefficient and the grey input coefficient. Additionally, researchers like Hsu [8] and Nguyen et al. [15] developed $GM(1,1)$ models incorporating residual correction techniques to reduce forecasting errors. Zhou et al. [16] established a new formulation called the $NGBM(1,1)$ by redefining the model's governing equation, while Hsu [8] further optimized its parameters using a

genetic algorithm. Chen et al. [17] proposed the Nash NGBM(1,1), integrating the concept of Nash equilibrium into the model framework. Furthermore, several hybrid models based on GM(1,1) have been introduced, such as the grey-Markov model [18, 19] and the grey-fuzzy model [12]. Although these modifications have significantly improved prediction performance, the GM(1,1) model inherently exhibits a monotonic prediction trend, which may limit its applicability in scenarios requiring more dynamic forecasting behavior.

The recently developed fractional-order accumulated grey model $GM^r(1,1)$ is a new grey forecasting model [20]. It has a fractional order accumulation of r that can effectively manifest the priority of new information of real systems and flexibility determines the level of linear, and an enhanced ability to handle complex, noisy, and uncertain data. It is particularly beneficial for systems exhibiting complex dynamics and long-range dependencies. That reason why the fractional-order accumulated grey model $GM^r(1,1)$ was applied in many cases. Wu and his peers successfully applied fractional accumulation to the fuel production of China [20], tourism demand [21] and electricity consumption [22], high technology equipment [23].

All these improvements focus on the model parameters and the background value. Actually, the initial condition is also an important factor determining the grey modeling accuracy. This is because the initial condition is a part of the predictive function. The current paper aims to develop an approach to increase the predictive precision of the $GM^r(1,1)$ by modifying the residual error obtained from $GM^r(1,1)$ with Trigonometric series. The practical application in the number of tourist forecasting to Quang Ninh shows that the proposed Trigonometric- $GM^r(1,1)$ model has higher performance on $GM^r(1,1)$ prediction. The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. A brief introduction to the fractional-order accumulated grey model and the residual error modification of $GM^r(1,1)$ model by Trigonometric series are given in Section 3. Section 4 proves the effectiveness of proposed approach in forecast the number of tourists visit to Quang Ninh. Finally, the paper concludes with some comments in Section 5.

2 Related Work

Wu et al. (2014) in short communication in already using grey model with fractional order accumulation to predict gas emission, this result show that the predicted performance of fractional order accumulation grey model is higher than among other model in three case studies [20]. One year later, Wu also applied fractional GM (1,1) model to predict the life of complex equipment, this result indicated that the fractional GM (1,1) show the effectiveness prediction with the lowest MAPE for in-sample and out-of sample data [23]. With the flexibility of fractional order accumulation r base on the priority of new information, the model has shown promising results.

After few years, many scholars using this model to explore in the real case. Zeng (2018) used the fractional order accumulation grey model to predict the total energy consumption in China and the monthly sales of new products in an enterprise. The result of this paper showed that the proposed model will be enhance the prediction accuracy [22]. Vu and Phan (2023) used the $GM^r(1,1)$ model to forecast the number of tourists visit to Quang Ninh Province, Vietnam. The empirical results show that the proposed model will get a higher accuracy performance with the lowest MAPE =19.722% [21].

All above research focus on the improvement of the accuracy of model by changing the parameters and the background value. In this study provide the different way to enhance the prediction performance.

3 Materials and Methods

3.1. A brief introduction to the fractional- order accumulated Grey model “GM^r (1,1)”

GM^r (1,1) is a fractional-order accumulated and single - variable grey model with an interpolated coefficient in the background value [20]. For predication involving linear small sample time series, its performance is better than that of the original grey forecasting models. The procedures involved for using the GM^r (1,1) can be summarized as follows:

Step1: Let the non-negative original data sequence X₀

$$X^{(0)} = \{x^{(0)}(1), x^{(0)}(2), \dots, x^{(0)}(k), \dots, x^{(0)}(n)\} \quad n \geq 4 \tag{1}$$

Where n is a total number of modeling data

Step 2: Construct a new series data X^(r) by using fractional-order accumulated generating operation (abbreviated as *r-AGO*)

$$X^{(r)} = (x^{(r)}(1), x^{(r)}(2), \dots, x^{(r)}(n)) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & C_r^1 & \dots & C_{r+n-3}^{n-2} & C_{r+n-2}^{n-1} \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & C_{r+n-4}^{n-3} & C_{r+n-3}^{n-2} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 & C_r^1 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{2}$$

Step 3: Building the GM^r (1,1) model by establishing the *r*-order differential equation with one variable is expressed as:

$$x^r(k) + az^{(r)}(k) = b \quad z^{(r)}(k) = 0.5x^{(r)}((k) + (k - 1)), k = 2, 3, \dots, n. \tag{3}$$

Where $z^{(r)}(k)$ is the average value of consecutive data and is computed by following function:

$$z^{(r)}(k) = 0.5(x_k^r + x_{k-1}^r)$$

So, whiteness equation is the following:

$$\frac{dx^{(r)}(k)}{d(k)} + az^{(r)}(k) = b \tag{4}$$

The value of parameter “a” and “b” can be estimated by using least- square method. That is

$$\begin{bmatrix} a \\ b \end{bmatrix} = (A^T A)^{-1} A^T Y \tag{5}$$

Where

$$Y = \begin{bmatrix} x^{(r)}(2) - x^{(r)}(1) \\ x^{(r)}(3) - x^{(r)}(2) \\ \dots \\ x^{(r)}(n) - x^{(r)}(n-1) \end{bmatrix} \tag{6} \quad \text{and} \quad A = \begin{bmatrix} -z^{(r)}(2) & 1 \\ -z^{(r)}(3) & 1 \\ \dots & 1 \\ -z^{(r)}(n) & 1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{7}$$

Step 4: The solution of the equation (4) can be expressed as follows

$$\hat{x}^{(r)}(k) = \left[x^{(r)}(1) - \frac{b}{a} \right] e^{-a(k-1)} (1 - e^a) \tag{8}$$

Step 5: The simulations and forecasting value can be obtained by applying the fractional-order

inverse accumulated generating operator (abbreviated as *r-AGO*). Therefore, the fitted and predicted sequence is given $\hat{x}^{(0)}$ as:

$$\hat{X}^{(0)} = (\hat{x}^{(0)}(1), \hat{x}^{(0)}(2), \dots, \hat{x}^{(0)}(n)) = [\hat{x}^{(r)}(1), \hat{x}^{(r)}(2), \dots, \hat{x}^{(r)}(k), \dots, \hat{x}^{(r)}(n)] \begin{bmatrix} 1 & -C_r^1 & \dots & (-1)^{n-1} C_{r+n-2}^{n-1} \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & (-1)^{n-2} C_{r+n-3}^{n-2} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & -C_r^1 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

3.2 Modifying the residual error of GM^r (1,1) by Trigonometric series

In order to improve the prediction accuracy of fractional- order accumulated Grey model, the Trigonometric series was used to modify the residual error of the GM^r (1,1). The overall procedure to obtain the modified model is as the followings [15]:

Let x is the original series of m entries and v is the predicted series (obtained from GM (1,1)). Based on the predicted series v , a residual series named ε is defined as:

$$\varepsilon = \{\varepsilon(k)\}, k = 2, 3, \dots, m \quad (10)$$

$$\text{Where } \varepsilon(k) = x(k) - v(k), k = 2, 3, \dots, m \quad (11)$$

According to the definition of the Trigonometric series, the residual sequence of GM^r (1,1) can be approximately expressed as:

$$\hat{\varepsilon}(k) = b_{(0)} + b_{(1)}(k) + b_2 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{L}(k)\right) + b_3 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{L}(k)\right) + \omega_k, k = 1, 2, 3, \dots, m \quad (12)$$

Where L is a user-specified parameter for the period of the main cyclic variations and ω_k is the random component. Therefore, the residual series is rewritten as:

$$\varepsilon = P \cdot C \quad (13)$$

Where

$$P = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{L}\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{L}\right) \\ 1 & 2 & \sin\left(\frac{4\pi}{L}\right) & \cos\left(\frac{4\pi}{L}\right) \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ 1 & n-1 & \sin\left(\frac{2(n-1)\pi}{L}\right) & \cos\left(\frac{2(n-1)\pi}{L}\right) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

$$\text{And } C = [b_1, b_2, b_3] \quad (15)$$

The parameter b_1, b_2, b_3 are obtained by using the ordinary least squares method (OLS) which results in the equation of:

$$C = (P^T P)^{-1} P^T \varepsilon^T \quad (16)$$

Once the parameters are calculated, the modified residual series is then achieved based on the following expression:

$$\hat{\varepsilon}(k) = b_{(0)} + b_{(1)}(k) + b_2 \sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{L}(k)\right) + b_3 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{L}(k)\right) + \varepsilon_k \quad (17)$$

Note that the constant term and the trigonometric terms in Eq. (17) can be treated as a part of Fourier residual model when L is equal to $n-1$.

From the predicted series v and $\hat{\varepsilon}$, the Trigonometric modified series \hat{v} of series v is determined by:

$$\hat{v} = \{\hat{v}_1, \hat{v}_2, \hat{v}_3, \dots, \hat{v}_k, \dots, \hat{v}_m\} \quad (18)$$

Where

$$\hat{v} = \begin{cases} \hat{v}_1 = v_1 \\ \hat{v}_k = v_k + \hat{\varepsilon}_k \quad (k = 2, 3, \dots, m) \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

3.3. Evaluative precision of forecasting models

In order to evaluate the forecast capability of the model, Means Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) index was used to evaluate the performance and reliability of forecasting technique [24]. It is expressed as follows:

$$MAPE = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{k=2}^m \left| \frac{x^{(0)}(k) - \hat{x}^{(0)}(k)}{x^{(0)}(k)} \right| \times 100\% \quad (20)$$

Where $x^{(0)}(k)$ and $\hat{x}^{(0)}(k)$ are actual and forecasting values in time period k , respectively, and n is the total number of predictions. Nguyen et al. [15] interprets the MAPE results as a method to judge the accuracy of forecasts, where more than 50% is an inaccurate forecast, 20%-50% is a reasonable forecast, 10%-20% is a good forecast, and less than 10% is an excellent forecast.

4 Validation of the Trigonometric- GM^r (1,1) Model and It's Application in Forecast the Number of Tourists visit to Quang Ninh

4.1 Collection and setting data

Located in the Northeast of Vietnam, Quang Ninh is the only province nationwide sharing land and sea borders with the People's Republic of China. The province covers a land area of 6,102 square kilometers and a sea surface area of over 6,000 square kilometers. There are 13 administrative units at district level, 177 units at communal level, 1,543 villages, hamlets and quarters. Its total population is about 1.34 million people belonged to 22 ethnic groups.

Quang Ninh also has more than 600 historical - cultural relics and other famous landscapes, many of which have become favorite destinations chosen by domestic and international tourists, such as: Bai Tu Long Bay, Bai Tu Long National Park, Co To Island, Quan Lan, Tra Co, Tuan Chau, Yen Tu Complex of Monuments and Landscapes, Cua Ong Temple Special National Monument... The World Heritage of Ha Long Bay alone, along with Bai Tu Long Bay and beautiful islands, if exploited and promoted to the fullest potential, can turn Quang Ninh into a world tourism center. Exploiting the advantages of resources and promoting the combined strength for tourism development, the achievements brought to Quang Ninh tourism in recent times are very encouraging. In 2019, Quang Ninh attracted more than 14 million visitors, of which international visitors reached 5.7 million, total revenue from tourists reached approximately 30,000 billion VND. With the position and role of Quang Ninh tourism, the Vietnam Tourism Development Strategy to 2030 has identified Quang

Fig 1: Map of Quang Ninh province

Ninh as one of the key tourist areas of the country, combined with Hai Phong, Hanoi, Ninh Binh to become a driving force for tourism development in the Red River Delta and Northeast Coast. [25]

The number of tourism visited to Quang Ninh province from 2011- 2022 were statistic by the Department of Tourism, Quang Ninh province and are visualized by Figure 2 [26].

As can we see the Figure 2, the number of tourists to Quang Ninh has increased steadily since year 2011 to 2019. Especially, the number of tourists increased by 1.5 times during the period time 2016 to 2019. However, the number of tourist visits to Quang Ninh province significantly dropped from 14,005,090 people in 2019 to 8,843,000 people in 2020 and continues to fall to 4,830,000 people in 2021. It is easy to explained the reason of significantly dropped in the number of tourism arrival to Quang Ninh is that COVID-19 pandemic.

In order to demonstrate the superiority of proposed approach, this study using the samples data from 2011 to 2022 (12 data points) to built the model. And then compared the result of proposed model and old one.

Fig 2: The number of tourists visited to Quang Ninh during the period time 2011-2022

4.2 Tool and functions

For calculation and simulation of $GM^r(1,1)$ and Trigonometric- $GM^r(1,1)$ model, this research will use Microsoft Excel of Microsoft Corporation. This is a common software among users and multiple functions are integrated for calculation. Beside a basic function in excel, Excel software also offers two useful functions named Mmult (array 1, array 2) to return the matrix product of two relevant arrays and Minverse (array) to return the inverse matrix. They are two fundamental calculations of in model parameter values. After executing these calculations by Microsoft Excel. Forecasting results of two models is shown below.

4.3 The forecasted performance of $GM^r(1,1)$ and Trigonometric - $GM^r(1,1)$ model

In combination with the data set and algorithm of $GM^r(1,1)$ and Trigonometric - $GM^r(1,1)$ models which is indicated in section 3.1 and 3.2, respectively, this research found out the parameter value $a = -0.0094$ and $b = 403181.8$ and $r = 0.01$ of $GM^r(1,1)$ and the parameter of b_0, b_1, b_2, b_3 . The results of both models for forecasting the number of tourist arrival to Quang Ninh as follow:

Table 1: Forecasted and error values of GM^r (1,1) and Trigonometric - GM^r (1,1) model

Actual value		GM ^{0.01} (1,1)		Trigonometric - GM ^{0.01} (1,1)	
Year	$x^{(0)}(k)$	$\hat{x}^{(0)}(k)$	Residual error (%)	$\hat{x}^{(0)}(k)$	Residual error (%)
2011	6,459,000	-	-	-	-
2012	7,000,000	6,860,973	1.99	6,905,944	1.34
2013	7,500,000	7,295,338	2.73	6,945,781	7.39
2014	7,500,000	7,742,596	3.23	7,568,137	0.91
2015	8,600,000	8,198,135	4.67	8,594,833	0.06
2016	8,350,000	8,660,217	3.72	9,724,821	16.46
2017	9,800,000	9,128,032	6.86	10,627,262	8.44
2018	12,246,000	9,601,157	21.60	11,045,769	9.80
2019	14,005,090	10,079,357	28.03	10,879,473	22.32
2020	8,843,000	10,562,497	19.44	10,214,890	15.51
2021	4,830,000	11,050,502	128.79	9,298,365	92.51
2022	11,589,000	11,543,334	0.39	8,457,816	27.02
MAPE (in data samples)			20.13	18.34	
Accuracy (%)			79.87 %	81.66	
Evaluation			Reasonable	Good	

Table 1 show that the MAPE index of proposed model is lower than the GM^r (1,1) model is 1.79%. These results indicate that the forecasted performance of proposed model is enhance the accuracy performance of GM^r (1,1) in this situation. In addition, figure 2 emphasize that the curve of Trigonometric - GM^(0.01) (1, 1) extremely closed with actual data than the curve of GM^(0.01) (1,1) model.

Fig 3: The visualization of $GM^{(0.01)}(1,1)$ and Trigonometric- $GM^{(0.01)}(1,1)$ model

4.4. The number of tourism arrival to Quang Ninh in the year of 2025 and 2028

By comparison the accuracy between these two forecasting models aforementioned, this research propose the use of Trigonometric - $GM^{(0.01)}(1,1)$ model to forecast the number of tourist visit to Quang Ninh during the period between 2025 and 2028 because the accuracy of Trigonometric - $GM^{(0.01)}(1,1)$ model is better than $GM^{(0.01)}(1,1)$ forecasting model. The number of tourism arrival to Quang Ninh during the period from 2025 to 2028 was illustrated in Table 2.

Table 2: The number of tourist arrival to Quang Ninh from 2025-2028

Year	Number of tourists arrival (Units: people)
2025	8,788,905
2026	9,872,196
2027	11,057,110
2028	12,013,651

From the results of Table 2, we can see that the number of tourist visit to Quang Ninh province continue to significantly grow during the next few years. To be more detailed, the number of tourism will reach 8,788,905 peoples in 2025 and this number is projected to hit the milestone of more than 12 million peoples in the year of 2028. This will be an important data resources for orientation and planning management agency so as to boost the development of upcoming tourism activities in Quang Ninh.

5 Conclusions

This study introduced an enhanced forecasting model, the Trigonometric-GMr (1,1), which incorporates a trigonometric series to modify the residual errors of the $GM^r(1,1)$ model. Based on the real case to predict tourist arrivals in Quang Ninh province, empirical results indicated that the Trigonometric- $GM^r(1,1)$ model delivers superior performance, achieving the lowest MAPE among the compared models.

By the way, the simulation results in forecast the number of tourist visit to Quang Ninh will be an important data resources for orientation and planning management agency so as to boost the development of upcoming tourism activities. In the future direction, this study will be modified

with other ways like Markov Chain to improve the the accuracy of the GM^r (1,1) model and will be applied this model to expand on these findings and to forecast performance of different industries.

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